

1 A165S, 1 C165A, 4 C165S, 2 L165C, 4 L165S, 3 S165A, 4 S165C, 2 S165L



- A
- S
- C
- {CS}
- L
- {GS}
- {CL}

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 A165S, 1 C165A, 4 C165S, 2 L165C, 4 L165S, 3 S165A, 4 S165C, 2 S165L



- A
- S
- C
- {CS}
- L
- {GS}
- {CL}

- Bathybatini
- Benthochromini
- Boulengerochromini
- Cyphotilapiini
- Cyprichromini
- Ectodini
- Eretmodini
- Gobiocichlini
- Haplochromini
- Heterotilapini
- Lamprologini
- Limnochromini
- Perissodini
- Serranochromini
- Steatocranini
- Tilapiini
- Trematocarini
- Tropheini

0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 A165S, 1 C165A, 4 C165S, 2 L165C, 4 L165S, 3 S165A, 4 S165C, 2 S165L



0 2 4 6 8 10 12

1 A165S, 1 C165A, 4 C165S, 2 L165C, 4 L165S, 3 S165A, 4 S165C, 2 S165L



0 2 4 6 8 10 12